

THE ISSUE OF CREDIT IN ISLAM

Murodkhonov Mukhammad Sodiq

Student of Kokaldosh secondary special school under
the Muslim Board of the Republic of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6740043>

Annotation: The Central Bank plans to adopt a law on non-bank credit institutions, which includes the concept of Islamic finance. Non-banks will be given the right to provide more services. In 2021, the Central Bank drafted a law on non-bank credit institutions, which includes the concept of Islamic finance. This was announced by Deputy Chairman of the Central Bank Behzod Hamrayev at a press conference at AOKA on 11 January. Shavkat Mirziyoyev made the proposal in an address to parliament on December 29. This article discusses the issue of credit in Islam.

Keywords: Islam, credit, banking, law, Muslims, justice, mechanism, law.

The head of state instructed the Central Bank to consider a draft law on non-bank credit institutions by February 1 to strengthen competition in the financial market, as well as to create a legal framework for the introduction of Islamic financial mechanisms. An Islamic bank is a financial activity that conforms to the principles of Sharia. It is forbidden to receive interest or rates in Islamic banking, depending on the amount and term of the loan. The ban is explained by Muslim laws on social justice and equality. Non-banks will be given the right to provide more services. In early September, a bill on non-bank credit institutions and micro finance was discussed, but it did not specify Islamic finance. The draft presidential decree, submitted for discussion in May 2018, states that Uzbekistan plans to create Islamic banking and financial infrastructure. The document provided for a ban on bonuses in the form of interest, and the distribution of profits and losses in proportion to the share in the project with the entrepreneur. It was also planned to develop regulations on insurance, leasing, securities transactions, based on the principles of Islamic finance.

A loan is a relationship of accumulating idle funds in the form of a loan fund and lending them to legal entities and individuals in need of money for production and other needs for a certain period of time, with repayment of interest. There are commercial, banking, government, consumer, international, mortgage and other forms of credit. A Commercial Loan is issued by a business entity and is usually formalized by a promissory note. Bank Loans - issued by banks to individuals and legal entities in the form of money. Bank loans come in the form of forfeiting, factoring, and lending to customers. Public Credit -

involves the participation of the state as a lender and borrower. The state, as a lender, finances the sector, region, enterprises from the budget through the banking system by allocating loans. As a borrower, the population borrows from individuals or legal entities through the sale of government bonds and bonds, resulting in domestic public debt, external public debt through loans from foreign countries. Consumer loans are loans to the population for the sale of consumer goods and services on credit, housing construction costs, pawnshops, mutual aid loans and other forms. International Credit - a loan in cash or in kind from a lender in one country to a borrower in another country on fixed-term, repayable and interest-bearing terms, as well as capital investment in foreign bonds, shares of foreign companies and securities.

Islamic banking is a banking activity based on the principles of Sharia and is a practical guide through the development of the Islamic economy. Shari'ah prohibits the charging of interest or surcharges for lending, regardless of whether it is recorded or paid. It is forbidden to invest in enterprises that supply goods or services (such as alcohol) that are contrary to Islamic principles. Although these prohibitions have historically been applied to some extent in the late twentieth century, several banks have been established to apply these principles to private or semi-private commercial establishments in the Muslim community. As of 2009, there were more than 300 banks and 250 joint funds established in accordance with Islamic principles in the world. In 2014, the total assets of \$ 2 trillion were adjusted to Sharia principles. As of 2014, Sharia-based financial institutions accounted for 1 percent of total global assets.

In summary, Islamic finance in Uzbekistan is presented in the form of Islamic Bank's private sector development projects. Financing is provided in the form of providing financing lines to banks to provide guarantees in accordance with the principles of Murobah'a. This is one of the most common ways of doing interest-free transactions used by banks in Muslim countries. Murobah'a is an active customer financing operation that is suitable for a wide range of purchases: from equipment to business premises. The principle of its operation is simple: the customer agrees on the terms of purchase of the desired goods and applies to the bank, which in turn buys the goods and sells them to the customer in parts for an additional fee.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. B.Y. Xodiyev, Sh.Sh. Shodmonov - "Economic Theory" - 2017
2. R.R. Khusainov - "Finance and Taxes" - 2014
3. A. Vahobov, A. Jorayev - "Taxes and Taxation" - 2009

4. I.A. Zavalishina - "Taxes: Theory and Practice" - 2005
5. D. Tadjibayeva - "Theory of Economics" - 2003